

Kinetics of Stepwise Aquation of Bis(Diethylenetriamine)-Chromium(III) Cation to Triaquodiethylenetriaminechromium(III) Cation in Acid Solution

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Bis (diethylenetriamine) chromium(III) perchlorate has been prepared by a modified method. The aquation of this compound in acid solutions has been investigated and the data were found to be fitted best by a three step reaction in which the fastest step occurred first and the slowest step last.

GARNER and co-workers¹⁻³ have published a series of papers on the aquation of series of linear amine complexes of chromium(III), the results of which show conclusively that the amine functions are replaced in stepwise fashion, and that the steps usually go from faster to slower but that the rate constants do not vary much from one step to the next of the unwinding process. The observation has also been made that the rate constants involved for species with the same number of aquo ligands are always closely related.³

In this paper we report the aquation of bis (diethylenetriamine) chromium(III) cation, which starts with six amine functions and aquates through three steps to give the triaquo product. The rate constants found decreased from the faster to the slower, but vary little from step to step.

Experimental

Reagents—All reagents used were of the highest available grade. Diethylenetriamine (dien) was obtained as Eastman Kodak Technical Grade and purified by standing over NaOH for several hours and then vacuum-distilling the supernatant liquid. The middle one-third cut was taken, assuming it to be diethylenetriamine of purity as high as the subsequent steps warranted.

Chromic chloride was obtained as Analytical Reagent Grade ($\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and it was found that the basic salts present were easily converted by storing the reagent under concentrated HCl. Quantities of the salt were then removed as needed, washed with very small volumes of water and acetone and dried.

Standard HClO_4 solution was prepared from reagent grade 72% HClO_4 . Standard NaClO_4 solution was prepared by neutralizing strong HClO_4 solutions of accurately known concentration with strong NaOH solution and diluting to volume.

Solvents used were 95% ethanol, absolute ethanol, reagent-grade acetone, reagent-grade petroleum ether (low boiling) and deionized water.

Methods of Analysis :—Chromium. The complex salt (0.1 g) was weighed into a porcelain crucible, wet with 3 drops of conc. sulfuric acid, 8 drops of conc. nitric acid and fumed almost to dryness. About 5 ml of water and 2-3 drops of conc. sulfuric acid were added and the solution evaporated to dryness and ignited over a micro-burner. The solid residue was transferred (dry) as well as possible to a beaker, and the material adhering to the crucible was loosened by fuming with about 4-6 ml conc. sulfuric acid and transferred. The mixture was diluted to about 100 ml with water, boiled, a few small crystals of silver nitrate were added and then solid ammonium peroxodisulfate was added in excess and the mixture boiled. The oxidation at this point was not complete, there being large quantities of chromic oxide still undissolved. Evaporation of the solution to a syrupy consistency, however, brought the oxide into solution. The solution was again diluted to 100 ml and the peroxodisulfate treatment repeated. The dichromate was titrated with standard ferrous ammonium sulfate solution, using sodium diphenylamine sulfonate as an indicator.

Perchlorate. About 0.2 g of the complex was dissolved in 30 ml of water and a 10% excess of 0.025M tetraphenylarsonium chloride was added dropwise. The mixture was allowed to stand, with constant stirring, for 45 min before filtering through tared gooch crucibles fitted with glass fiber filter pads. The precipitate was dried at 105° for 70 min and weighed as tetraphenylarsonium perchlorate. Optionally, the filtrability of the precipitate can be improved vastly by ageing the precipitate for several hours at room temperature. Control experiments on standard perchloric acid solutions and on standard solutions of chromic chloride, diethylenetriamine and perchloric acid indicated that the perchlorate analysis ran from 0.5-1.0% low on the latter solutions, indicating possibly some interference.

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Preparations

Bis(diethylenetriamine)chromium(III) sulfate: A hydrated chromium sulfate-water-diethylenetriamine mixture could be made to react at 100-120°C at pressures below atmospheric within 5-15 hours, but the product was always contaminated with varying amounts of a violet, water-insoluble fraction. Filtering the reaction mixture, washing the product with 95% ethanol, absolute ethanol and acetone and drying in a vacuum-desiccator over CaCl_2 produced yields up to 60%.

Bis (diethylenetriamine)chromium(III) chloride :

A modification of a method proposed by Schlafer and Kling⁴ was used. To 26.6 g $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ completely dissolved in 410 ml of absolute alcohol was added dropwise, 25 ml of diethylenetriamine, the mixture was heated just below its boiling point for 1.5 hr. The temperature was then raised and the ethanol was distilled off. An additional 25 ml of diethylenetriamine was added and the solution was heated for 9 hr. on the steam bath with a gentle stream of dry air passing over the surface. The yellow-brown solid was separated, washed with ethanol and ether and was dried. Yield 50-56%.

Bis (diethylenetriamine)chromium(III) perchlorate :--(Caution)⁵ Crude sulfate (8.0 g) or chloride (7.3 g) was dissolved in 12 ml of 1.7 M HClO_4 ; this was centrifuged to remove any precipitate. The resultant solution was added drop-wise to 30 ml of 8 M HClO_4 at 0°. After letting stand for 10 min. with constant stirring, the product was filtered, sucked dry, and was washed with absolute alcohol and petroleum ether. Yield, 3.5-5.0 g of air dried material.

The crude perchlorate was recrystallized twice by dissolving in minimum volumes of 1.7 M HClO_4 , filtering, then cooling the filtrate in an ice bath for 25-45 min. Yield, 15-40%. Anal.—Calc.: Cr 9.34, ClO_4 53.59%; Found: Cr 9.23, ClO_4 52.9%.

Methods of Measurements.—All absorption data were obtained in method 10-cm cells on a Cary Model 14 Recording Spectrophotometer with cell compartment thermostatted to $\pm 0.05^\circ$ using standard 0.1000 N HClO_4 - 0.894 M NaClO_4 reference solution. A scan speed of 1 nm/sec was chosen so that errors in absorbance readings due to the slope of the recorded curve and to the difference in times of points along the spectra were negligible.

Absorption curves were taken in the range 600 to 300 nm in preliminary runs and 530 to 300 nm in nearly all subsequent runs. In certain exceptional cases, as in the photochemical effect check, time-wise readings were only taken at selected wave lengths, in this case, at 350, 450 and at 520 nm.

Solutions. All kinetic runs were conducted on solutions 1.00 mM in bis (diethylenetriamine) chromium (III) perchlorate, 0.1000 M in HClO_4 and 0.894 M NaClO_4 . The ionic strength of this solution was 1.000 and it was determined that it remained constant, to

within 0.3%, during the entire course of the reaction. The pH changed only to the extent of 0.02 units during the portion of the reaction studied. Short runs made in 0.2000 N and 0.1500 N HClO_4 with an amount of NaClO_4 which maintained ionic strength at 1.000 showed that there was no significant hydrogen ion dependence.

Results

Measurement of the absorption curves for solutions of several different concentrations of bis (diethylenetriamine) chromium (III) perchlorate at 10° showed that this compound conformed to the Beer-Bouguer Law at all wave lengths studied.

Complete spectra were recorded periodically (time depending on the rate of the reactions) at each 5 degree interval between 15 and 30°.

Figure 1. Absorption spectra of bis(diethylenetriamine)chromium perchlorate as a function of time at 30.0°.

A family of curves obtained at some of the times during the course of a 30.0° run is shown in Fig. 1. From the complete set of runs at this temperature several isosbestic points are apparent. During the initial part of the reaction, isosbestic points occurred at 374, 398 and 489 nm. These disappeared at the end of about 3 hr and at about 7 hr a new well-defined isosbestic point emerged at 507 nm, and disappeared at about 20 hr.

Since curves were recorded at relatively frequent intervals, with solutions otherwise kept in darkness, comparisons were made between absorbance readings obtained at 30.0° in kinetic runs involving different amounts of exposure to the spectrophotometer light source. These results showed no significant photochemical effect.

Treatment of Data.—Guggenheim has shown that for a simple first-order reaction $A \xrightarrow{k} B$

$$\ln(A - A') = -kt + \ln(A_0 - A_\infty) (1 - e^{-k\Delta t}) \\ = -kt + \text{constant}$$

where A and A' may be measurements, at time t and $t + \Delta t$, respectively of a physical property of the initial and final species A and B , k is the rate constant, A_0 and A_∞ are the initial and the final values of the measured property, and Δt is a constant time increment. Plotting $\ln(A - A')$ vs. t yields a straight line whose slope is equal to the rate constant.

The extension of this technique to the analysis of a two-step system involves plotting $\ln(A - A')$ vs. t and extending the straight line portion of the curve which becomes dominant in the later stages of the reaction. By plotting the log of the differences between the experimental $(A - A')$ values and those for points on the straight line vs. t , a second straight line is obtained. If the two rate constants differ to a sufficient degree, the smaller of the rate constants may be calculated from the slope of the first line and the larger from the slope of the second.

Treatment of the data by this extension of the method of Guggenheim gave two rate constants the value of each of which were generally about the same at most wavelengths, and gave evidence that there might be a third at some wave lengths. At 30° the first two were $3.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and $7.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. These are sufficiently close to each other that a more complete analysis of the data was undertaken.

It is common knowledge that a linear kinetic system

can be described mathematically by the exponential series

$$A_3 = a_0 + a_1 e^{-k_1 t} + a_2 e^{-k_2 t} + a_3 e^{-k_3 t}$$

where the a 's are known functions of the molar absorptivities of the individual species and the k 's. For a three-step system

$$a_0 = \epsilon_D A_0 d$$

$$a_1 = \frac{A_0 d}{(k_2 - k_1)(k_3 - k_1)} (\epsilon_A(k_2 - k_1)(k_3 - k_1) \\ + \epsilon_B k_1(k_3 - k_1) + \epsilon_C k_1 k_2 - \epsilon_D k_2 k_3)$$

$$a_2 = \frac{A_0 d}{(k_2 - k_1)(k_3 - k_1)} (-\epsilon_B k_1(k_3 - k_2) \\ - \epsilon_C k_1 k_2 + \epsilon_D k_1 k_3)$$

$$a_3 = \frac{A_0 d k_1 k_2}{(k_3 - k_2)(k_3 - k_1)} (\epsilon_C - \epsilon_D)$$

$$\text{Solving } \epsilon_A = \frac{1}{A_0 d} (a_0 + a_1 + a_2 + a_3)$$

$$\epsilon_B = \frac{1}{A_0 d} (a_0 + \frac{(k_1 - k_2)}{k_1} a_2 - \frac{(k_3 - k_1)}{k_1} a_3) \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon_C = \frac{1}{A_0 d} (a_0 + \frac{(k_3 - k_2)(k_3 - k_1)}{k_1 k_2} a_3) \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon_D = \frac{a_0}{A_0 d}$$

A computer program was written to fit the data to an exponential equation (1) by using the values obtained from the Guggenheim analysis as the first approximation, allowing all parameters to vary, (2) taking the average rate constants found in fitting the 7.5–20 hour data, attempting to fit only a two term exponential series, and (3) using the two exponential term values for the estimation of a third exponential term.

The direct fit to a three exponential term equation was not successful in general, but the fit to a two exponential term equation was successful and a third rate constant only slightly larger than the larger of the first two rate constants was indicated. Because of the difficulty and the doubt about the value of the third term this fit was only made for the 15 and 30° data. The advantage of this method is that the experimental data are fitted directly and the deviations can be interpreted in terms of the original data. The average deviations of the fitted absorbance over 19 different wave lengths for the 15° data was 0.0013.

Figure 2. Values ϵ_B for various options of reaction rates. 1) Fastest reaction first, 2) Intermediate speed reaction first, 3) Slowest reaction first. The range indicated by the arrows are for the λ_{max} values of known chromium compounds with 5-N ligands and 1-0 ligand.

Having a set of data fitted with an exponential series does not establish the order of the various terms. Because of this the molar absorptivities of the intermediates B and C were calculated using equations 2 and 3. The values of ϵ_B are plotted in

Figure 3. Values of ϵ_C for various options of reaction rates. 1) Slowest reaction last, 2) Intermediate speed reaction last, 3) Fastest reaction last. The range indicated by the arrows are for the A_{max} values of known chromium compounds with 4-N ligands and 2-O ligands.

Fig. 2 and the values of ϵ_C are plotted in Fig. 3. The values indicated by the ranges between the arrows are the expected A_{max} for Cr with 5-N ligands and 1-O ligand in Fig. 2 and for 4-N ligands and 2-O ligands. The rate constants used for these calculations at 30° were 8.6×10^{-5} , 6.4×10^{-5} and $3.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. The conclusions that may be drawn from these figures are from Fig. 2 that the fastest rate occurs first and from Fig. 3 that the slowest rate occurs last.

The rate constants determined for the two exponential term equation are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS DETERMINED BY FIT OF THE TWO TERM EXPONENTIAL EQUATION

T(°C)	$10^5 k_1 (\text{sec}^{-1})$	$10^5 k_2 (\text{sec}^{-1})$
15.0	1.18 ± 0.08	0.36 ± 0.003
20.0	2.0 ± 0.1	0.83 ± 0.01
25.0	4.2 ± 0.2	1.45 ± 0.05
30.0	7.5 ± 0.5	3.1 ± 0.2

The values for E_a were calculated from the data in Table 1 and gave 22.4 kcal/mole for the faster step and 25.1 kcal/mole for the slower step. The order of

the rate constants is the same as that reported for the aquation of triaquodiethylenetriaminechromium(III) by Lin and Garner,¹ and the E_a values are reasonable when compared with their values.

Bis(diethylenetriamine)chromium(III) can exist in three geometric isomeric forms, the meridional, and the two facial isomers, one with the secondary nitrogens trans and one with them cis. The existence of the meridional form is extremely unlikely. Ion exchange experiments on our compound at 5° over an extended period of time showed only a single band. This does not establish that the starting compound was a single isomer, but it does permit the supposition that it may have been.

The argument made by Lin and Garner¹ against the rupture of a secondary amine bond to chromium is certainly applicable here. No matter which of primary nitrogens one thinks of detaching from one of the facial isomers, the result will be an intermediate which consists of a stereoisomeric pair. Then if one detaches the second primary nitrogen one gets a single product which will have only to lose the secondary nitrogen to become the triaquo product. It is extremely unlikely that the path would be by a mixed pathway involving isomerization because the isomerization reactions are much slower.

References

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5. Because of the reported explosive nature of cobalt(III) and chromium(III) hexaamine perchlorates all operations in the preparation of this salt should be done with care. The final product was found to be sensitive to heat, detonating violently at 299° and above.